

ISic2748

I.Sicily inscription 2748

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary; honorific

Material

tuff

Object

painted wall

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2015.03.26; 2014.09.11

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

from the so-called forum

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 6381

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]ΤΩΝ
2. [---]ΛΚΑΙΡΟΝ
3. [---]ΑΙΔΕΥΟ
4. [---]ἀρετὰν
- 4a. [---]

Apparatus

Text after IG

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645151

PHI 140355

PHI 336188

Bibliography

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- 1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 49.1331.1
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Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità.* At 371
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